

KOMPLEKS TEKISLIKDA BIRLIK AYLANANING KO'PHAD OSTIDA INVARIANTLIGI

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19812812>

Annotatsiya: Kompleks dinamik sistemalar tushunchasi kompleks analizning asosiy yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib, u ko'p yillar davomida rivojlanib kelmoqda. Ko'plab matematiklar kompleks dinamik sistemalar bilan shug'ullangan va hozirgi kunda ham ushbu soha kengayishda davom etmoqda. Kompleks dinamik sistemalar ko'plab amaliy tadbirlarga ega. Gaston Julia, Pierre Fatou, shuningdek John Milnor va boshqa ko'plab olimlar ushbu sohaning rivojlanishiga katta hissa qo'shganlar. Kompleks dinamik sistemalarda invariant to'plam tushunchasi muhim ahamiyatga ega. Agar markazi koordinata boshida bo'lgan birlik aylana ko'phad ostida oldinga invariant bo'lsa, ko'phadning qanday ko'rinishda ekanligini quyida keltirilgan teoremdan bilish mumkin.

Abstract: The concept of complex dynamic systems is one of the fundamental branch of complex analysis, which has been developing for many years. A lot of mathematicians have been engaged in complex dynamic systems, and also nowadays this field is expanding. The complex dynamic systems have many practical applications. Gaston Julia, Pierre Fatou as well as John Milnor and many other scientists had contributed to the development of this field. The concept of invariant sets plays an important role in complex dynamical systems. If the unit circle centered at the origin is forward invariant under a polynomial, then the form of this polynomial can be determined by the theorem presented below.

Aytaylik bizga D ($D \in \bar{\mathbb{C}}$) sohada f funksiya berilgan bo'lsin.

Ta'rif 1. Agar $f(D) \subset D$ bo'lsa, D soha f da oldinga invariant deyiladi.

Ta'rif 2. Agar $f^{-1}(D) \subset D$ bo'lsa, D soha f da orqaga invariant deyiladi.

Teorema 1: $P(z)$ - darajasi d ($d \geq 2$) ga teng bo'lgan ko'phad bo'lsin. Agar $C = \{|z|=1\}$ birlik aylana uchun $P(C) \subset C$ bo'lsa, u holda $P_d(z) = \alpha z^d$ ($|\alpha|=1$).

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